

#13

Evaluation & Impact Assessment **MIND MEITHEAL (MIND COMMUNITY)**

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING INTERROGATING CREATING ADDRESSING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Stages in a project where different actors/stakeholders interact.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Small to large, up to approx. 100 people.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No technical skills required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>2-4 hours (including preparation).</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>For large networking events, graphic design assistance is preferable, which can cost in the region of €1000.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tool #5.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: Teagasc

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Facilitate co-creation of an *aspirational* multi-actor social network map, including all the actors who should *ideally* be involved in an initiative.
- Engage actors to become involved and facilitate networking between them.
- Periodically update the map to include more actors, where appropriate.
- Use the aspirational social network map to assess progress in engaging actors and in facilitating networking between them.

Background and Logic

Meitheal is a word in the Irish language, which simply means 'work team'. It is historically associated with people in the same community coming together to undertake collective work. In many ways, the concept is consistent with ideal conditions for interactive innovation, in the sense that actors come together willingly to co-innovate for mutual benefit. While other tools (e.g. Tool#1 in this toolbox) generate social network maps that depict the actors who are actually involved in a project/initiative and how they are cooperating together in 'real-life', this tool generates an aspirational depiction of an ideal social network: who are all the actors who should ideally be involved, and how should they cooperate together? Co-creation of such an aspirational picture should be undertaken by a multi-actor group, involving actors who see potential from very different perspectives. Once an aspirational map is co-created (depicting both actors who should become involved and the collaborative ties between them), it can be used as a guide to progress the development of the relationships needed, as well as to assess progress in that regard.

This tool provides a guide for the co-creation of an ideal social network map and practical ways of engaging new actors and building collaborations between them. How to use the map for assessing progress towards creating an ideal social network is described.

Materials

- Thick black markers
- Sticky-notes
- Camera/phone camera.
- Graphically designed social network map & customised name badges & colour-coded stickers for affixing to name badges. This is well described in the [film](#), depicting the tool's use.

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1: Preparation

- Explain the purpose, logic and background of the tool.
- Optionally, show a [film](#) of the use of the tool for networking in a heritage grains multi-actor Horizon 2020 project, [CERERE](#).

Step 2: Co-create an Aspirational Social Network Map

- Issue post-it notes and markers to participants.
- Optionally, if Tool #1 (Participatory Social Network Mapping) was used, revisit the map created and ask participants to modify it to create an 'ideal' type – including all desirable actors for inclusion in a particular project/initiative.
- Otherwise, facilitate participants to brainstorm all desirable actors needed for a particular project/initiative. The actor types are written on sticky notes by participants (providing assistance where required). The sticky notes are placed on flip chart paper, on a board or table (several pieces of flip chart paper may be joined together with tape, accommodating a larger social network).
- Once all actors have been identified, invite participants to cluster the actors – can they be categorised into a smaller number of cohorts (where similar actors are clustered together)? Note: this step may be unnecessary if actors are different from each other. Actors in different sectors (e.g. primary production, retail, innovation brokering, education, marketing etc.) may stay apart.
- Ask participants to draw lines (using marker), indicating where cooperation between actors is necessary. Extra thick lines can be drawn by participants to indicate cooperation between actors that is particularly vital.
- The output of Step 2 is a Social Network Map that identifies all desirable actors to be involved in an initiative and illustrates the collaborations required between actors within the initiative, with the importance of collaborations highlighted.
- Photograph the aspirational Social Network Map.

Step 3: Preparation for a Networking Event

- Use the completed aspirational Social Network Map to design a networking event.
- First, commission a graphic designer to create a professionally produced version of the map, or create a version using (free) software such as [Gephi](#) (requires technical expertise in social network mapping) or [Mural](#) (requires basic technical expertise).
 - » Each of the actor categories should be colour coded (as pictured). A legend should accompany the social network map, indicating which actor category corresponds to each colour.
 - » Stickers (round discs) should be available/customised to match the colours used in the legend.
 - » A large poster version of the social network map is printed for display at the social networking event. It is vital that it is sufficiently large so that actors participating in the event can view it. Another option is to project an image of the social network map onto a screen.
- Actors representing each of the actor categories in the social network map are invited to the networking event. Participants who created the social network map can use their contacts, and the facilitator makes contact with organisations/associations to identify new actors. It is important to add as many actors as possible from outside existing social networks, enhancing diversity. The number of actors invited per category depends on the budget/venue available and the needs/orientation of the project/initiative.
- Choose any venue for the networking event. If possible, it is worth considering having an event themed according to the topic of the project/initiative, possibly with a contribution from public artists. This makes the event more engaging, enjoyable and the environment will stimulate more ideas. This is the approach followed in the [film](#), where a Horizon 2020 project partnered with an experienced [public artist](#) and an established [arts festival](#).

- Once a confirmed list of participants in the social networking event is available, name badges are printed/hand-drawn. The name of the person should be printed in large font, allowing participants in the event to easily find and identify each other.
- The output of Step 3 is that a venue and list of diverse participants are confirmed for the social networking event. Actors identified in the aspirational social network map are represented in the confirmed list of participants. Name badges have been printed, with some blank badges available for unexpected participating actors. Stickers that match the colours of the legend in the social network map are available (a sufficient number – at least one of each colour for confirmed participant – remaining stickers can be used for future events). The large image of the social network map is ready for display at the venue.

Step 4: Social Networking Event

- Actors arrive at the social networking event and are invited to view the social network map. Facilitators/ hosts are at hand to explain that they may select the colour/s of the actor category/ies to which they feel they belong. Actors may choose more than one category. On the basis of their choice/s, actors are provided with sticker/s, which are affixed in a visible position on their name badge.
- Actors are invited to observe the social network map – can they identify potential collaborators from the map, or can they identify other collaborators on the map they would like to network with at the event?
- Actors circulate and identify each other, discussing mutual interests, and forging nascent collaborations.

Step 5: Use of Social Network Map & Networking Event for Assessment and Evaluation

- Contact can be made with participants in the aftermath of the event in a variety of ways to assess the impact of the social networking event. A questionnaire may be issued, or phone/online contact may be established to answer the following types of questions:
 - » Did you meet any potential collaborators at the event?
 - » Did you exchange contact details / forge a new collaboration with anyone and if so who?
 - » Is there any other actor who wasn't present, who you would like to collaborate with (relevant to the topic of the event/project/initiative)?
 - » It is important to note that there are learnings from answers to the above question that are relevant not only in relation to the social networking event, but in relation to the project/initiative overall. Who are we seeking to engage with? Is our chosen selection of actors complete? Are there other actors we should consider? Such questions are important for improving reflexivity in developing/forming the ideal (multi-actor) social network, setting optimal conditions for interactive innovation.
- The aspirational social network diagram produced by this tool can be compared to the actual social network diagram (produced, for example, by Tool#1 of this toolbox). Actions may be planned, for instance using Tool#12, to progress the aspired diversity of the social network.
- The actual versus aspirational social network diagrams may be compared periodically to assess progress in diversifying the social network to achieve the ideal social network.

